

Reactive Imides as Curing Agents for Epoxy Resins. Part-1. Synthesis and Characterisation

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A series of low molecular weight amine-terminated amide-imides (ATRs) has been prepared by reacting a dicarboxylic acid containing an imide group and diamines for use as curing agents for epoxy resins. The ATRs have been characterised by nitrogen analysis, viscosity, vapour pressure osmometry (VPO) and spectral data. Molecular weights of ATRs are in the range 400–700. X-Ray diffraction shows these reactive imides which are in general soluble in polar solvents to be mostly amorphous.

Epoxy resins are one of the most widely used matrix materials for composites¹. The major limitation of these resins is their limited thermal stability. One way of improving this property is to use new curing agents which can impart thermal stability to the resultant networks. Generally various amines are used as curing agents for epoxy resins. The nucleophilic nitrogen atom of amine curing agents appears to initiate thermal degradation by loss of water molecules at the secondary hydroxyl groups. If a thermally stable group that can reduce the basic character of the nitrogen atoms is present in the curing agent, the nitrogen atom becomes a weaker nucleophile thereby the thermal stability of the network is expected to be improved. The use of aromatic imide groups as well as maleimides as heat-resistant curing agents has been reported². Incorporation of an amide-imide group into a diamine may work in the similar line and the resultant compound is, therefore, expected to impart superior thermostability to the cured epoxy composite when used as the epoxy curing agent. However, this reduction in basic character of the amines results in their lower reactivity and hence longer cure times and/or higher temperatures for curing may be necessary to achieve optimal curing.

With this background in mind we have conducted an investigation³ to synthesise a series of amine-terminated low molecular weight amide-imides by reacting a dicarboxylic acid containing an imido group with different diamines to be used as curing agents for epoxy resins. The present paper reports the synthesis and characterisation of these amine-terminated amide-imides.

Results and Discussion

Synthesis of IDCA: Synthesis of IDCA is obtained by the reaction between TMA and PABA in highly polar solvents like NMP, DMF etc.

At about 70° TMA and PABA react to form an amide acid or better known as amic acid.

The cyclisation resulting in the formation of the imide group occurs at higher temperatures.

As the solubility of the resulting IDCA in DMF is limited even at 130°, part of it is precipitated as a yellow mass during the reaction period. The reaction product may contain, apart from IDCA, unreacted TMA and PABA. The TMA and PABA are removed by suspending the precipitate in alcohol in which both of them are soluble.

Synthesis of ATRs: Polyamideimides can be synthesised by different methods⁴⁻⁸. However, thionyl chloride activated low temperature polycondensation technique for the synthesis of polyamides and polyesters, has been suitably adopted for the synthesis of polyamideimides directly from imidodicarboxylic acids.

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In general, the polyamideimide formation may be represented as

Ueda *et al.*⁵ used hexamethyl phosphoric triamide (HMPA) or NMP as solvents and pyridine or 2,6-lutidine as acid acceptors. In their later work⁶ pyridine was used as a solvent-cum-acid acceptor for the synthesis of polyamides and polyesters. In our laboratories NMP or DMF was tried as a solvent for the polycondensation of imidodicarboxylic acid with different diamines^{6,7,11}. For the preparation of low molecular weight amine-terminated amideimides, NMP, pyridine and DMF were tried as solvents and in all the cases the products were identical.

The ATRs may be represented as

In order to prepare very low molecular weights, ATRs, the molar ratio of IDCA to diamine used is 1 : 2.25.

IDCA were characterised by nitrogen analysis and ir spectroscopy. The details of the characterisation were reported in our earlier publications^{5,6,12}. Physical characteristics and analytical data of ATRs are presented in Table 1. Five ATRs were prepared by reacting IDCA with five diamines, viz. MDA, mPDA, PACM, HMDA and EDA, designated as ATR_{MDA}, ATR_{mPDA}, ATR_{PACM}, ATR_{HMDA} and ATR_{EDA}, respectively. All the ATRs are generally soluble in polar solvents. When the

amine used in the preparation of the ATR is aromatic, the resultant ATR is soluble in the highly polar solvents such as DMF, DMAC, DMSO, NMP etc., very sparingly soluble in ketone solvents such as 1,4-dioxane, tetrahydrofuran etc. and insoluble in halogenated solvents, hydrocarbons etc. In the case of ATRs from cycloaliphatic or aliphatic amines, the resultant ATRs are partially soluble in highly polar solvents, but soluble in pyridine and tetrahydrofuran, and insoluble in most other solvents.

Ir spectra: The strong absorptions of the imide group at 1775, 1720 and 720 cm^{-1} confirm its presence in the molecules. Similarly the strong absorptions at 1650 and 1525 cm^{-1} confirm the presence of amide group. The broad peaks at 3400–3500 cm^{-1} show the presence of primary amine groups in the molecules. Also aromatic primary amines absorb at 1340–1250 cm^{-1} due to the C–N stretching. The band at 1250 cm^{-1} is relatively stronger in the spectra of ATR_{MDA} and ATR_{mPDA}. This may be attributed to the presence of not only the amide groups (which result in a weak band) but also the aromatic primary amine. The weak band present at 1410 cm^{-1} in the spectra

of ATR_{PACM}, ATR_{HMDA} and ATR_{EDA} may be attributed to the C–N vibration of aliphatic primary amine groups in their molecules. The absorption peaks at 1600 and 1510 cm^{-1} in all the spectra may be attributed to the aromatic skeletal vibrations involving carbon-carbon stretching within the ring (The aromatic rings originated from IDCA). The 1600 cm^{-1} band is stronger in the spectra of ATR_{MDA} and ATR_{mPDA}; this is because of the completely aromatic character of the molecule. The spectrum of ATR_{MDA} contains a sharp absorption peak at 1410 cm^{-1} and this is characteristic of exclusive *para*-substitution in the molecule.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF ATRs

ATR*	Colour	Density g cm^{-3}	M.p. $^{\circ}\text{C}$	η_{in} dl/g	\bar{M}_n	N % : Found/ (Calcd.)
ATR _{MDA}	Yellow-brown	1.32	178–180	0.10	680 ^a 671 ^b	8.89 (8.88)
ATR _{mPDA}	Yellow-green	1.31	228–229	0.11	500 ^a 491 ^b	10.94 (10.97)
ATR _{PACM}	White	1.12	239–240	—	695 ^b	8.95 (8.66)
ATR _{HMDA}	Yellowish white	1.34	214–215	—	507 ^b	10.09 (10.74)
ATR _{EDA}	Brownish white	1.39	285–287	—	395 ^a	7.58 (12.54)

*The diamine used for the synthesis of respective ATR is shown as the suffix of the ATR.

**Measured in 0.5% (w/v) solution in DMF at 32°, for other ATRs it could not be determined due to their very low solubility in DMF. ^aMeasured by VPO. ^bDetermined from equivalent weight.

¹H nmr spectra : ¹H nmr spectroscopy has been used to characterise only two ATRs viz. ATR_{MDA} and ATR_{mPDA}. In the former, the complicated multiplets at δ 7.2–8.7 arise due to the 23 aromatic protons along with the 2 amide protons. The hump at δ 4.3–5.2 is attributed to the 4 aromatic primary amine protons. The peak at δ 3.95 is due to the 4 protons of the two methylene groups between the benzene rings. The two peaks at δ 2.76 and 2.94 are due to the traces of residual DMF, which was used as a solvent in the preparation and purification of the material. The peak at δ 2.5 is due to the residual DMSO present in DMSO-d₆ used as the solvent. The other peaks including the one at δ 3.15 have not been identified and they may be due to impurities.

The ¹H nmr spectrum of ATR_{mPDA} is similar to that of ATR_{MDA}. The multiplets at δ 7.00–8.70 give an integration of 15 aromatic protons along with the 2 amide protons. The hump at δ 3.2 to 3.8 is due to the 4 aromatic primary amine protons. As in the previous spectrum the peaks due to the residual DMF and DMSO are observed at the respective positions.

X-ray diffraction : The absence of sharp peaks in the diffraction patterns of ATRs suggests that these materials are non-crystalline substances; particularly ATR_{mPDA} and ATR_{PACM} can be termed as completely amorphous. On the other hand, the remaining ATRs show a few broad hump suggesting that certain order exists in their structures and hence they are, to a certain but small extent, crystalline.

For a molecule to have crystallinity its atoms/groups (elements) should be arranged symmetrically in its unit cells; for this the molecule should possess certain flexibility which will allow the elements to position themselves properly during the crystallisation process¹³. The presence of aliphatic chain in the molecule makes it possible to get certain crystallinity. Thus ATR_{HMDA} containing chains of 6 carbon atoms and ATR_{EDA} containing ethylene groups show greater amounts of crystallinity. The higher densities and higher melting points of ATR_{HMDA} and ATR_{EDA} may be explained to be due to the close packing of the molecules.

Experimental

Trimellitic anhydride (TMA; Chemalog), 4,4'-bis(aminocyclohexyl)methane (PACM-20; DuPont) and 4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane (MDA; E. Merck) were used as such. *p*-Aminobenzoic acid (PABA; E. Merck) was recrystallised from hot distilled water. Thionyl chloride (SD Fine Chemicals) was freshly distilled. Triethylamine (B.D.H.) was dried (potassium hydroxide) and distilled. *m*-Phenylenediamine (mPDA; B.D.H.) was purified by distillation under reduced pressure (~30 torr). Hexamethylenediamine (HMDA; Fluka, Switzerland) was purified by distillation under nitrogen

atmosphere. Ethylene diamine (EDA; B.D.H.) was purified by drying (sodium hydroxide) followed by distillation under nitrogen atmosphere. *N*-Methylpyrrolidone (NMP; Fluka) was dried over phosphorus pentoxide for 24 h and then distilled under reduced pressure (~20 torr). Dimethylformamide (DMF; E. Merck) was kept over freshly ignited magnesium sulphate for 24 h and distilled under reduced pressure (~20 torr). Pyridine (B.D.H.) was refluxed with solid sodium hydroxide and then distilled. All other chemicals and solvents used were of analytical grade and used as received.

Imidodicarboxylic acid (IDCA) : It was prepared by reacting TMA with *p*-aminobenzoic acid. The detailed procedure was reported elsewhere¹².

Amine-terminated amide-imides (ATRs) : Low molecular weight ATRs were prepared by thionyl chloride activated low temperature polycondensation technique using IDCA and excess amount of different amines. The amines used were MDA, mPDA, PACM, HMDA and EDA. To dry IDCA (15.55 g, 0.05 mol), DMF (120 ml) was added with stirring. The mixture was cooled to -5° and cold thionyl chloride (7.5 ml) was added. The reaction mixture was then allowed to cool to about 0° and triethylamine (13.5 ml, 0.9 mol) was added. The stirring was continued and when the temperature was about -5°, the required amine (0.1125 mol) in DMF solution was added. The temperature was maintained at about -5° and the reaction was continued for about 5 h with stirring. The reaction mixture was then slowly poured into vigorously stirred ice-cold water. The resulting solid was washed with excess water repeatedly. The products were then suspended in a well-stirred 5% aqueous solution of sodium bicarbonate for about 2 h, filtered and the residue washed with water. The residue was then suspended in alcohol or acetone for about 10 h, filtered and washed with alcohol or acetone and dried in a vacuum over (50–60°), yield 70% ATRs were purified by precipitation from DMF solution with methanol and dried under reduced pressure at 60°.

Ir spectra (nujol/KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 B spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Varian EM 930 spectrometer (90 MHz) using trimethylsilane as the internal standard. X-ray diffraction pattern was recorded with a Dorn I (USSR) diffractometer using Ni filtered CuK_α radiation.

Density was determined at 32° with a Pyknometer using cyclohexane as immersion liquid. Viscosity was measured in DMF solution (0.5%, w/v) using a Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer. The molecular weights of the DMF-soluble-amide-imides were determined by vapour pressure osmometry (VPO) at 90° using benzil as the standard and DMF as the solvent with a Knauer (Germany) vapour pressure osmometer.

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